

PROFILE OF BLOOD DONORS IN THE CITY OF BURGAS DURING THE PERIOD 2020–2024**Georgieva L.***Doctoral candidate in the Department of Health Management and Health Economics, Faculty of Public Health „Prof. Tzekomir Vodenicharov, MD, DSc”, Medical University – Sofia***Zlatanova T.***Professor in the Department of Health Management and Health Economics, Faculty of Public Health „Prof. Tzekomir Vodenicharov, MD, DSc”, Medical University – Sofia*

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ABSTRACT

Blood donation is a fundamental component of modern healthcare systems and ensures the availability of safe blood components for patients. The aim of this study was to analyze the demographic profile of blood donors in Burgas, Bulgaria, during the period 2020–2024.

A retrospective observational study was conducted using data from the Department of Transfusion Hematology in Burgas. Donors were analyzed according to age, sex, and annual dynamics.

The results demonstrated a steady increase in the number of blood donors from 7,671 in 2020 to 9,176 in 2024. The most active donor group was aged 31–40 years. Men accounted for approximately 75–80% of all donors throughout the study period, while women remained significantly underrepresented.

The findings may support the development of regional policies aimed at strengthening voluntary non-remunerated blood donation.

Keywords: blood donation, blood donors, transfusion medicine, public health, demographics, Burgas.

INTRODUCTION

Ensuring an adequate supply of safe blood and blood components remains one of the major challenges facing modern healthcare systems. The World Health Organization identifies voluntary non-remunerated blood donation as the most reliable mechanism for ensuring the safety and sustainability of blood supplies.

In recent years, demographic changes, population aging, and migration processes have significantly affected the available donor pool. Analyzing the profile of blood donors is an important tool for planning transfusion medicine activities and for developing effective policies aimed at recruiting and retaining voluntary blood donors.

AIM

The aim of this study was to analyze the profile of blood donors in the city of Burgas during the period 2020–2024 according to age and sex and to identify the main trends in the development of the donor population.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A retrospective observational study was conducted using data from the Department of Transfusion

Hematology in Burgas for the period 2020–2024. Statistical data on the number of blood donors, categorized by age group and sex, were analyzed.

The following methods were applied:

1. Descriptive statistical analysis;
2. Comparative analysis;
3. Graphical trend analysis;
4. Analysis of the ratio between the number of blood donors and the population.

RESULTS

The analysis revealed a consistent positive trend in the number of blood donors throughout the study period.

The total number of blood donors was as follows:

1. 7,671 in 2020;
2. 6,753 in 2021;
3. 7,720 in 2022;
4. 8,400 in 2023;
5. 9,176 in 2024.

Overall, the data demonstrate a steady increase in donor activity during the study period, with the highest number of blood donors recorded in 2024.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

ANALYSIS

Following the period of restrictive measures imposed during the COVID-19 pandemic, a sustained recovery and subsequent increase in donor activity were observed.

The highest donor activity was recorded in the 31–35 and 36–40 years age groups. Throughout the entire study period, these groups constituted the core of the donor population.

A clear predominance of male blood donors was identified. Their relative share ranged between 75% and 80% of all donors, whereas women accounted for approximately one quarter of the donor population.

Among men, a distinct peak was observed in the 31–40 years age range, followed by a gradual decline after the age of 45. In contrast, the distribution among women was more evenly spread, with the highest level of donor activity recorded in the 41–55 years age groups.

The calculations indicate that in 2024 there were approximately 40.77 blood donors per 1,000 working-age residents in Burgas and 23.93 blood donors per 1,000 inhabitants of the total population.

Figures 1–5 illustrate several common trends observed throughout the study period:

1. The total number of blood donors showed a gradual increase over the years, rising from 7,671 in 2020 to 9,176 in 2024.
2. The highest numbers of blood donors were recorded in the 36–40 and 31–35 years age groups.
3. The lowest numbers of blood donors were observed among the oldest age group (61–65 years) and the youngest age group (under 20 years).
4. Men predominated among blood donors, accounting for nearly four times as many donors as women.
5. After the age of 50 years, the number of blood donors declined considerably.

Figure 6

The calculations indicate that in 2024 there were approximately 40.77 blood donors per 1,000 working-age residents in Burgas and 23.93 blood donors per 1,000 inhabitants of the total population.

In developed countries, the number of blood donors generally ranges between 33 and 50 per 1,000 population. In developing countries, this figure may fall below 10 donors per 1,000 population, often resulting in shortages of blood and blood components.

The results obtained for Burgas indicate a relatively high level of donor activity, approaching the levels typically reported in developed countries. This finding suggests a stable donor base and a favorable potential for maintaining an adequate blood supply for regional healthcare needs.

DISCUSSION

The results obtained are consistent with published international data regarding the demographic structure of blood donors. In many European countries, men constitute the majority of voluntary blood donors.

The lower participation of women may be explained by a combination of physiological, medical, and social factors. Lower hemoglobin levels, a higher prevalence of iron deficiency, pregnancy, and breastfeeding may limit the ability of women to donate blood regularly. Furthermore, women are more likely to refrain from blood donation due to health-related concerns.

The 31–40 years age group represents the core donor population. This may be attributed to higher levels of social activity, greater professional stability, and better overall health status compared with older age groups.

The relatively low proportion of young donors under the age of 25 highlights the need for more

intensive educational and awareness campaigns in schools and universities.

The findings support the need for targeted regional programs aimed at promoting voluntary blood donation and rejuvenation.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The present study is limited to data obtained from the Department of Transfusion Hematology in Burgas and does not encompass all potential factors influencing blood donation activity.

The following variables were not analyzed:

1. Educational status;
2. Occupational background;
3. Motivation for blood donation;
4. Frequency of repeat donations.

Future studies may incorporate sociological approaches to provide a more comprehensive analysis of the motivational factors associated with blood donation behavior.

CONCLUSION

During the period 2020–2024, a sustained upward trend in the number of blood donors was observed in the city of Burgas.

The predominant donor profile was a male donor aged between 31 and 40 years.

Women participated in blood donation considerably less frequently, although their proportion remained relatively stable throughout the study period.

The findings highlight the need for targeted measures aimed at attracting young people and increasing female participation in voluntary blood donation.

The results of this study may serve as a basis for the development of regional policies and strategies to ensure the sustainable growth and maintenance of the donor population.

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